

Compact Triple-Band Circularly Polarized Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna for Sub-6 GHz Applications

Manendra S. Chauhan¹, Nidhi Sharma², Sumita Sekhawat³, Poonam Tiwari⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Punjab Engineering College (Deemed to be University), Chandigarh, India

²Department Physics, Dhanauri P.G. College, Dhanauri, Haridwar Uttarakhand, 247667, India

³Department of Physics, Kanoria PG Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Rajasthan, Jaipur, India

⁴Department of Physical Sciences, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, 304022, India

Abstract

This work presents a compact triple-band circularly polarised (CP) rectangular dielectric resonator antenna (RDRA) optimised for Sub-6 GHz fifth generation (5G) applications. A novel method is devised to realise the proposed antenna design that enables compactness, triple band operation, and high performance. Two RDRAs working in three different configurations provide CP. Triple-band operation is achieved by the excitation of TE₁₁₁ mode (Top and Side view) at frequency 3.75 GHz for RDRA1 and TE₂₁₁ mode (Top view) for RDRA2. Compactness is achieved through the hybrid structure and the excitation of modes beyond the fundamental one. It can be seen that the antenna indeed presents gains close to 8.2 dBi with more than 90% radiation efficiency. The design adopted a 72 × 72 mm² FR4 substrate with defected ground structure (DGS) having a cross-slot. RDRA1 is attached to a rectangular patch with a microstrip feed. At the same time, RDRA2 is located on the top of the cross-slot of the ground plane. Designed and simulated from Alumina (Al₂O₃), RDRAs are optimized to minimize dielectric loss while enhancing energy transfer. The judicious choice of materials and strategic placement of components greatly enhance the antenna's electromagnetic performance, resulting in advanced impedance matching and bandwidth over the target frequency bands.

Index terms: Dielectric Resonator Antenna, Multi-band, Circularly Polarized, 5G.

Introduction

Wide use of the 5th generation mobile network in the construction of a new power system, with its characteristic high bandwidth and low delay, promotes an increasing demand for high-speed communication, as seen in. Among them, the substation will become a typical application scenario of 5G communication in the new power system, especially for the need for digital transformation of the power system. It is estimated that in the period of the "14th Five-Year Plan", the market demand capacity of 5G substations in China will reach 2.112 billion yuan [2]. However, the electromagnetic environment in the substation is complex, and many 5G terminals are distributed. The 5G base station antenna is the basic equipment to provide 5G communication needs in the substation, and its site selection will not only affect the quality of 5G communication in the substation but also affect the electromagnetic compatibility of the equipment in the station [3]. The unreasonable site selection of the 5G base station antenna is not conducive to the development of the 5G substation and even endangers the safe and stable operation of the power system in serious cases. Therefore, it would be very important to study the location selection scheme of the 5G base station antenna concerning 5G communication quality in the substation and electromagnetic compatibility of equipment in the station [4].

In the current 5G scenario, CP antennas become very important to meet the requirements and challenges in the future toward the realization of next-generation wireless devices. Below the Sub-6 GHz band, the coexistence of cellular, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and IoT technologies is operated simultaneously. The use of a CP

antenna will mean that just one antenna could be used for wideband operations, thereby allowing efficient use of the spectrum. They also offer enhanced spectrum utilization, compatibility, multiband functionality, flexibility, and cost efficiency, which is very important in wireless communication working under this frequency range [5]. DRA provides attractive features of high radiating efficiency, compact size, high gain, multimode functionality, etc. while considering the antenna design for CP. The shape of the DRA may be rectangular, cylindrical, deformed shape, etc., and there are many feeding designs available like microstrip feeding, coaxial probes, co-planar waveguides (CPW), and aperture coupled [6]. DRs are made of dielectric material and they resonate strongly at certain frequencies depending on the dimensions and material properties [7]. By adjusting the dimensions, the resonant frequency of a DRA can be tuned accordingly to reconfigure it at various operating frequencies within a specified range. The possibility of frequency tuneability thus makes DRA adaptable to different frequency bands, which is an important factor in versatile wireless communication systems [8]. Also, the DRAs can provide a relatively wide bandwidth that enables it to support several frequency bands in a corresponding frequency range. Especially, this wideband feature is very suitable for frequency reconfigurable antennas, which can support many wireless communication standards and applications. The DRAs have small sizes, hence easily embedded into small devices for applications without degrading performance. Therefore, CP in DRAs can achieve compact wideband antennas, which enlarge adaptability and improve the overall performance. While traditional DRAs are valued because they possess the following qualities: low profile, high radiation efficiency, and compatibility with integrated circuits, they usually have no frequency agility and thus adapt poorly to changing communication needs.

A summary of the comparison of the proposed antenna with previous works is shown in Table 1. This paper presents a new CP RDRA. With the continuous development of wireless communication systems, DP antennas have become very important in these systems. These antennas may change their characteristics gain, polarization, increased radiation efficiency, and improved radiation patterns to meet the demands of a particular system. The designed antenna is compact and lightweight; hence, it is inexpensive. Besides, some of the switching techniques in reconfigurable antennas are reviewed with the dual purpose of indicating their adaptability and possible improvement in communications systems.

Table 1. Comparison between the proposed antenna with previous work

Ref.	Antenna	Physical Size (mm ³)	Gain (dBi)	Radiation Efficiency [%]	Complexity	CP
[11]	Fluidic DRA	-	6.76	88	Complex	No
[12]	DRA with the air gap	-	4.9	78	Complex	No
[13]	Differential Fed DRA	-	3	91	Simple	No
[14]	DRA	150 × 100 × 3.38	2.7	92	Complex	No
[15]	DRA	50 × 57 × 4	3.52	90	Complex	No
[16]	DRA	45 × 33 × 2.78	3.02	89	Complex	No
[17]	DRA	36 × 20 × 5.57	1.69	-	Complex	No
[18]	Hybrid DRA	-	2.74	-	Simple	No
This Work	Hybrid DRA	72 × 72 × 1.6	8.2	95	Simple	Yes

The attractive features of the proposed antenna are as follows:

- Compact size: $72 \times 72 \times 1.6$ mm³.
- The DGS with a cross-slot adds resonant modes, enhancing impedance matching and widening bandwidth for effective multi-frequency operation.
- The precise placement of the two RDRA boosts resonance and coupling, enhancing antenna efficiency and radiation.

- FR4 and Alumina (Al_2O_3) offer low dielectric loss and optimal thickness, ensuring efficient energy transmission with minimal losses.
- The microstrip feed, paired with the DGS and resonators, ensures effective energy transfer and robust performance across targeted frequency bands.

The structure of the paper is outlined as follows: Section 2 describes the design methodology and optimization techniques for the proposed antenna. Section 3 goes into the mathematical analysis involving CP antennas but narrows the application to sub-6 GHz bands. Section 4 presents the results simulated using CST software. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the key findings of the research and offers some directions for future research.

Antenna Configuration

The proposed antenna configuration and design parameters are illustrated in Fig.1. The setup features two Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antennas (RDRA), a Microstrip Feed, and a $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ substrate with a defected ground structure (DGS) incorporating a cross-slot on the bottom side. RDRA1 is positioned atop a rectangular patch with a microstrip feed, while RDRA2 is located directly above the cross-slot on the ground plane. The rectangular ring-shaped patch is printed on an FR4 epoxy substrate, characterized by a relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of 4.4 and a loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) of 0.02, with a substrate thickness of $H_s = 1.6 \text{ mm}$. Both RDRA are fabricated from Alumina (Al_2O_3), which possesses a relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of 9.8 and a loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) of 0.02. RDRA1 has a radius of 9 mm and a height of 5 mm. Fig. 2 provides a perspective view of each component, while the symbolic parameters of the proposed antenna are detailed in Fig. 3. Further dimension specifications can be found in Caption 3. The strategic placement of RDRA1 and RDRA2 enhances the antenna's electromagnetic performance by optimizing resonance and coupling effects. The defected ground structure with a cross-slot introduces additional resonant modes, improving impedance matching and bandwidth. Choosing materials, such as FR4 and Alumina, is crucial for balancing performance factors like dielectric loss, substrate thickness, and overall antenna efficiency. The microstrip feed, combined with the defected ground and resonators, enables effective energy transmission, minimizing losses and ensuring the antenna operates effectively across the intended frequency bands.

Fig.1. Configuration of proposed CP RDRA

Fig.2. Configuration of proposed CP RDRA

Fig.3. Symbolic parameters for respective dimensions

$W=L=72\text{mm}$, $P1=33.6\text{mm}$, $P2=28.80\text{mm}$, $T1=2.26\text{mm}$, $T2=40\text{mm}$, $T3=2.26$, $A1=33.60\text{mm}$, $A2=20.16\text{mm}$, $B1=27.84\text{mm}$, $B2=8.64\text{mm}$, $H1=12\text{mm}$, $H2=4.8\text{mm}$, $C1=4.8\text{mm}$, $C2=9.12\text{mm}$, $C3=1.48\text{mm}$, $C4=1.48\text{mm}$.

Mathematical Modelling

The antenna proposed in this study is a hybrid design that integrates various features to improve its performance. The resonant frequency is influenced by the presence of two dielectric layers, namely FR4 and Alumina. The effective height (H_{eff}) and the effective permittivity (ϵ_{reff}) are key parameters that define the behaviour of this antenna. As outlined in [16], the H_{eff} , effective permittivity ϵ_{reff} and the resonant frequency $f_{0,ring}$ can be calculated using Equations 1-3.

$$H_{eff} = H + H_S \tag{1}$$

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{H_{eff}}{\frac{H}{\epsilon_{rCDRA}} + \frac{H_S}{\epsilon_{rSub}}} \tag{2}$$

$$f_{0,ring} = \frac{A_1 \times c_0}{(2\pi) \times R_2 \times \sqrt{\epsilon_{re}}} \tag{3}$$

Where, $A_1 = \frac{2 \times R_2}{(R_2 + T) + R_2}$ (4)

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{(\epsilon_{rSub} + 1)}{2} + \frac{(\epsilon_{rSub} - 1)}{2} \left(1 + \frac{10 \times H_S}{T} \right)^{-0.5} \tag{5}$$

Where, ϵ_{re} = relative permittivity Substrate, c_0 = Velocity of light in free space. Hence, by using equation (6), (7) and (8) the resonant frequency of the ring patch, $f_{0,ring}$ is calculated as 3.75 GHz.

$$H_{eff} = H + H_S \tag{6}$$

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{H_{eff}}{\frac{H}{\epsilon_{rRDRA}} + \frac{H_S}{\epsilon_{rSub}}} \tag{7}$$

Reference [25] indicates that the resonance frequency of the fundamental TE_{111}^z mode can be determined using a transcendental equation.

$$k_z \tan\left(k_z \frac{d}{2}\right) = \sqrt{(\epsilon_{reff} - 1)k_0^2 - k_z^2} \tag{8}$$

Where, $k_x, k_y,$ and k_z are wave numbers.

They satisfy the following equation

$$k_x^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2 = (\epsilon_{\text{reff}})k_0^2 \quad (9)$$

Where, $k_x = \frac{\pi}{b}$ and $k_y = \frac{\pi}{b}$

According to [26], the reconfigurable tuning range (TR) is given by equation 5:

$$\text{TR}(\%) = 2 \times \left(\frac{f_{\text{oh}} - f_{\text{ol}}}{f_{\text{oh}} + f_{\text{ol}}} \right) \times 100 \quad (10)$$

Where, f_{oh} = Higher resonating frequency and
 f_{ol} = Lower resonating frequency

Fig.4. Step evolution of the proposed design

It is an evolutionary process of the antenna, shown step by step in Fig. 4 to attain its optimum performance: A simple rectangular patch fed by microstrip and on a full ground plane represents Configuration 1; the basic setup gives standard radiation characteristics but with limited bandwidth and resonance capabilities. The middle of the patch in Configuration 2 is provided with a rectangular slot, and the patch becomes a rectangular ring, thus increasing its design tenfold. Due to this, current distribution is and bandwidth is increase, hence multiple resonant modes are achievable. More modulation is provided to the ground plane with a cross-shaped slot and a DRA is placed over that slot. The primary role of the cross-slot ground structure is to introduce defected ground modes that provide an enhancement in impedance matching and the creation of additional resonant frequencies. Locating the DRA over the cross slot further couples these modes and hence enhances the performance of the antenna. In Configuration 3, an RDRA is stacked upon the patch. A high dielectric constant is utilized in this geometry of the RDRA for confining electromagnetic fields within the resonator and thereby improving radiation efficiency further to enhance operational bandwidth. Thus, RDRA in combination with the already proposed cross-slot and rectangular ring forms a hybrid system that is support multiple higher-order modes. It hence presents a very compact but highly efficient antenna that is capable of operating within a wide frequency range with improved circular polarization and gain.

Results and Discussion

The antenna is fabricated and tested in three different configurations, namely, without DRA, with a grounded DRA, and with both DRAs. In the configuration without DRA, the S11 reflection coefficient is above -10 dB in the frequency ranges from 2.6-2.62 GHz (0.02 GHz bandwidth) and 3.73-3.82 GHz while

the resonant frequency comes at 2.61 GHz as depicted in Fig. 5(a). It is below 3 dB at 3.1-3.2 GHz, 3.4-3.5 GHz, and 4.3 GHz as shown in Fig. 6a. This setup has resulted in a gain of 7.1 dBi as depicted in Fig. 5d with a radiation efficiency of more than 0.4 dB or 40% as presented in Fig. 6b. In the grounded DRA arrangement, the S11 is above -10 dB within the frequency ranges from 3.12 to 3.23 GHz (0.12 GHz bandwidth), 3.18 to 3.35 GHz (0.17 GHz bandwidth), and 4.11 to 4.21 GHz (0.10 GHz bandwidth) with resonances at 3.1 GHz, 3.48 GHz and 4.1 GHz presented in Fig 5(a). The axial ratio is below 3 dB from 2.7-2.9 GHz and 3.2 - 3.8 GHz as shown in Fig. 6(a), providing a gain of 6.9 dBi, shown in Fig. 5(d) and the radiation efficiency of more than 0.8 dB (80%) is given by Fig. 6(b).

Fig.5. Results of all three Configurations; (a) Reflection Coefficient (S11), (b) VSWR, (c) Impedance (Z₁₁), (d) Gain

Fig.6. Results of all three Configurations; (a) Axial ratio, (b) Radiation efficiency

Finally, with both DRAs in place, the S11 in the configuration exceeded -10 dB across the ranges 2.66-2.79 GHz (0.13 GHz bandwidth), 2.99-3.14 GHz (0.15 GHz bandwidth), and 3.72-4.11 GHz (0.39 GHz bandwidth) with resonances at 2.7 GHz, 3.75 GHz, 3.85 GHz, 3.94 GHz, and 4.05 GHz, as can be seen from Fig. 5(a). 6(a) shows less than 3 dB axial ratio within 2.6-2.9 GHz, occurring at 3.1 GHz, 3.3 GHz, and within 3.9-4.0 GHz and 4.2-4.3 GHz frequency ranges. This was accompanied by the largest gain among the configurations at 8.24 dBi, as depicted in Figure 5(d), and radiation efficiency greater than 0.9 dB (or 90%), as depicted in Figure 6(b). Additionally, Figure 5(b) shows the VSWR less than 2 at the resonant frequencies for all three configurations. Figure. 5(c) depicts that the input impedance Z11 is around 50 Ωs at resonance.

Table 2. Comparative results of all three configurations

Configuration	S ₁₁	Axial Ratio	Gain	Radiation Efficiency
Without DRA	>-10 dB from 2.6-2.62 (0.2GHz), 3.73-3.82 resonating at 2.61GHz	3dB<3.1-3.2, 3.4-3.5,4.3 GHz	7.1 dBi	More than 0.4 dB (40%)
With Ground DRA	>-10 dB from 3.12-3.23 (0.12GHz), 3.18-3.35 (0.17GHz), 4.11-4.21 (0.10GHz) resonating at 3.1, 3.48, 4.1 GHz	3dB<2.7-2.9, 3.2-3.8 GHz	6.9 dBi	More than 0.8 dB 80%)
With Both DRA	>-10 dB from 2.66-2.79 (0.59 GHz), 2.99-3.14 (0.15 GHz), 3.72-4.11 (0.39 GHz), resonating at 2.7, 3.75, 3.85, 3.94, 4.05 GHz	3dB<2.6-2.9, 3.1, 3.3, 3.9-4, 4.2-4.3 GHz	8.24 dBi	More than 0.9dB (90%)

Fig. 7 (a-d) illustrates the field distribution of the proposed CP antenna at a frequency of 3.75 GHz. Fig.7(a) presents the surface current distribution, highlighting the current flow over the antenna elements. Mainly current concentration is observed at the transmission line and rectangular ring-shaped patch. Fig.7(b) shows the electric field distribution on the top surface of the RDRA1 observed in the TE₁₁₁ mode, providing a detailed view of the field pattern in this area. Fig.7(c) offers a side view of the electric field distribution for the TE₁₁₁ mode at RDRA1, revealing the vertical variation of the field. Lastly, Fig.7 (d) displays the electric field distribution on the top surface of RDRA2, illustrating the field pattern associated with the TE₂₁₁ mode.

Fig.7. Field distribution of proposed CP antenna; (a) Surface current distribution, (b) Electric field distribution at Top RDRA 1 (c) Side view of electric field distribution at RDRA 1, (c) Top view of electric field distribution at RDRA 2

Fig.8. 2D Radiation patterns at resonant frequencies

The radiation patterns of the proposed antenna are depicted in Fig. 8 (a-b) for the frequencies of 2.7 GHz, 3.75 GHz, 3.85 GHz, and 4.05 GHz at XZ and YZ planes. These figures illustrate the antenna's radiation characteristics at each frequency, detailing how by antenna disperses energy into space. The patterns at 2.7GHz and 3.75 GHz show bidirectional radiation patterns. On the other hand, 3.85 GHz and 4.05 GHz provide a comprehensive view of the directional radiation properties and coverage of the antenna, offering insights into the distribution of radiated power and the shape of the radiation beam across the specified frequencies.

Conclusion

This study introduces a novel triple-band compact CP RDRA designed for 5G Sub-6 GHz applications. The antenna features a three-layer layout, offering a low profile and cost-effective solution with several key advantages. Through optimization, the antenna achieves an 8.24 dBi improvement in component isolation, ensuring minimal interference between its elements. Additionally, the proposed design delivers a high gain of 6.8 dBi, making it particularly well-suited for modern and future 5G Sub-6 GHz communication systems. The combination of its compact size and high performance makes this antenna a strong candidate for a wide range of wireless applications.

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